

Classification of Performance Degradation Issues In Virtualized Cloud Environments

Madhuri D. Tarapra[#]

Student of MCA
Marwadi University, Rajkot, Gujarat, India
Email ID: patelmadhavi91@gmail.com

Mitrarajsinh K. Jadeja

Student of MCA
Marwadi University, Rajkot, Gujarat, India
Email ID: mk.jadeja01@gmail.com

Jeba Praba. J[#]

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Computer Applications
Christ College, Rajkot, Gujarat, India &
Research Scholar, Marwadi University, Rajkot, Gujarat, India
Email ID: prabajjg@gmail.com

Dr. R. Sridaran

Dean
Faculty of Computer Applications
Marwadi University, Rajkot, Gujarat, India
Email ID: sridaran.rajagopal@gmail.com

These authors are considered as Joint first authors

Abstract: Besides the many advantages provided by the cloud, the associated forbidden behaviour namely the performance degradation is to be dealt with properly. The performance degradation occurs due to many reasons including the virtualization. The proposed survey aims at classifying the degradation based on the available literature. This hopefully will be useful for the researchers and cloud users.

Keywords: Cloud Computing; mitigation techniques; virtualization; Security Threats

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing provides ability of supporting large and capacious data with the help of a shared pool of resources and a huge volume of storage area [1]. There are diverse advantages of cloud computing; the most important ones are being lower cost, re-provisioning of resources and remote accessibility [2]. Lower costs, gain by ignoring much expenditure from an organization in planning the physical infrastructure by third party vendors. The cloud provides adjustable attributes user can instantly use; they add more resources when user wishes to grow their requirements. Remote accessibility provides facility to access cloud services from anywhere at any time.

Performance degradation is the key issue in cloud computing systems. In clouds, cluster based system architectures applied to various types of services. Each of them has large identical duplicate components which are extended on various PM (Physical Machines). The problem with a performance of the system is a labour-intensive task for developers to contain. These parts of the system are source of that particular problem. It would be advisable for developers to have sufficient tools to catch the underlying sources of performance problem in the system. The reasons for arising performance problems may be system design defects, code bugs, mis - configurations of key parameters as well as environmental problems [3]. The technology in the background

of cloud services is reflected to have small overhead running over processors with hardware-assisted virtualization features. This custom virtualization technology is also used in high-performance computing operations [4]. Performance degradation introduced by the virtualization layer in clouds (e.g., hypervisor). Performance estimate is routinely implemented based on the prototype in conformation with a conclusion. The criteria such as average waiting time, load balancing, requests, cost, throughput, workload, a rate of transactions, response time, various scheduling algorithms, effectiveness, delays in service and productivity, number of I/O operations in the network etc is used for performance estimate. [5]. This paper introduces some other virtualization layer or areas which effects on performance degradation in the cloud.

In this paper, the correct signification of cloud computing, as well as performance prototype and reflection, are explained in the alternative key outfit. Under the section II recently available performance degradation key areas and factors which affect performance in virtualized environments analyzed. In section III a semantic classification for another area of performance degradation in a virtualized environment is proposed.

II. RELATED WORK

Virtualization helps the efficient management of hardware resources used in an application, Pedro Freire Popiolek et al., [6] illustrates an approach to monitor and analyze of performance of an application in a virtualized environment. These authors have experimented on generating a synthetic workload by identifying the main cause of observed degradation of performance across different Operating Systems. And also, explained yet another factor that is responsible for performance degradation on a virtualized environment but none of these works have focussed on multiple aspects causing performance degradation.

Hui Zhao et al., [7] have worked on a real open stack cloud platform and analyzed the communications between VMs and shared Hardware and selects appropriate Physical Machine(PM) for placing a Virtual Machine(VM). VM performance models are to minimize the PM performance degradation. They have not focussed on performance models based on secondary level hardware like disk I/O.

Jianhuache et al., [9] presented an analysis on the performance of three open source virtual machine monitors- OpenVZ, Xen, and KVM which are adopted to container based virtualization called para-virtualization and full virtualization. Performance evaluation on VM monitors plays an important role in improving the design and dealt with main two higher version techniques of Xen and an Open-source KVM as the

Fig. 1. Classification of Performance Degradation at different areas

Haibo Mi et al., [8] explained an approach to rapidly diagnose the source of performance degradation in large-scale non-stop cloud computing systems. Trace techniques with two identifiers have been presented over here. The work does not consider experiments based on large- scale distributed systems and dealt with some techniques for performance problem detection using (i) Data Pre-processing (ii) Localizing the abnormal methods. These approaches may tend to find the roots of the problems more efficiently and accurately, but not having any broader perspective.

delegate of Full virtualization.

III. CLASSIFICATION DIAGRAM FOR PERFORMANCE DEGRADATION AT DIFFERENT AREAS

The schematic diagram described in Figure 1 gives the performance degradation in different areas. The diagram further exposes the performance degradation in a virtualization environment. The five important areas identified, namely, VMM /Hypervisor and Neighbours Noise, Guest OS, Guest

Resource Interdependence, Utilization Ambiguity and Network I/O Dependent. The multi-tenancy characteristics of cloud computing mean that multiple VMs can share the same physical nodes and degrade network performance. The next section deals with the elements affecting the performance degradation of cloud virtualization while Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS).

A. HYPERVISOR AND NOISE

The hypervisor is a term used in virtualization technology to refer to a software program with the capacity of managing multiple instances of the same or complexity different operating systems on a single computer. The different OS may share virtualized hardware resources such as processors, memory etc. On the other hand, a noisy neighbour describes a rogue virtual machine that monopolizes storage I/O resources, Bandwidth, CPU and other resources at the expenses of another virtual machine in the same environment [10]. With a noisy neighbour, other VM and applications sharing the same infrastructure and resources suffers from unequal cloud network performance.

Spinlocks refer to a synchronization technique mostly used in modern OS kernels [11]. In this a thread waiting to have a lock waits while actively monitoring the lock. In hypervisor, virtual CPUs (VCPUs) are scheduled on the actual CPU for time slice: this is done to achieve pseudo-parallel execution. Although spinlock is extensively used in applications to enhance synchronization, it leads to serious performance degradation on a virtual machine. For example, it causes LHP (Lock Holder Pre-emption) problem and LWP (Lock Waiter Pre-emption) problem. The two problems are as a result of excessive spinning by VCPUs which occurs as a result of waiting to acquire a spin lock.

The Lack of bandwidth also causes performance degradation by decreasing connectivity and showing down response time in a network. In VMs, dynamic migration across the physical machine has the ability to ensure that the high-level performance required for meeting SLAs is attained. As such the whole process requires a lot of internet bandwidth [13]. Lack of enough bandwidth, therefore causes performance degradation during the migration process.

After creation of a snapshot, some additional delta files are created by VMs, performing disk operations within the virtual machine lead to the recreation of disk I/O through parsing of each snapshot delta file in the chain [14]. As such, this creates an extra overhead on the host as this call for the opening of more than one file. The files must also be processes to recreate more I/O data for the guest OS. This finally translates to performance degradation of the whole system due to the extra overhead as a result of snapshots.

B. GUEST OS

The guest OS is an OS that is secondary to the first OS (host OS) installed in a computer system, the secondary operating

system is either a part of VM (virtual machine) or a portioned system [13]. The main aim of a guest operating system is to have an alternative OS on the computer. The version of the guest OS used in the virtual environment may cause performance degradation. The guest OS should always be the latest and regularly updated by the provider. Performance degradation is brought about by having the OS susceptible to viruses and malware which may slow the whole system [13].

The version of the guest OS depends on the alternative the user On-Demand basis. For example, a Windows 10 user may prefer to have an alternative Windows 7 running on the same machine.

A Windows user may also prefer to use a Linux OS on any Window OS, or use Window OS on Linux as guest OS. The configuration of the guest OS on host OS requires network configuration first on the guest OS profile (guest OS tab) here the network is configured either as domain or groups. Next, the Apply button is clicked to save either domain or workgroup. Finally, is to save the guest OS by either clicking apply to save setting if it's a new guest OS profile. If it's a guest OS page from template wizard, the button Next is pressed, next a name is typed in the name field and general tab the click Apply, the OK button. To set up network connectivity, the checkbox for allowing the host and guest to share the network should be checked [15]. When configuring the guest OS, accepting default configuration may sometime lead to performance degradation. It is, therefore, to carefully study the whole system before any configuration is done [16].

In a virtualized environment in most cases involves a number of guest systems all competing for limited HHD access, and CPU.As such, these redundant systems interact freely an in unexpected ways. Network connectivity may, therefore, reduce the traffic and hence reducing performance [16].

C. GUEST RESOURCE INTERDEPENDENCE

In virtualized machine, the resources are divided into virtual resources to enable sharing among the individual guest machine or VMs. As such, it helps to reduce wastage, by increasing already used capacity and therefore decreasing the many physical resources. Based on virtual machine configurations, some VM is given more preferences than others for some specific physical resources while losing preference for others. For example, in sharing of CPU, credit scheduler is used to allocate different VM, depending on weight value and cap value. For memory resources, reservation, maximum, and minimum value are used to assign it to different VM. While managing network resources, bridging and routing are used to ensure that it is well shared and utilized [10].

In a non-virtualized system, the following factors i.e. CPU, RAM, Storage, and Networking can be analyzed and isolated based on certain limitations that take into account the operating system interactions and workloads. Though in a virtualized environment, the results for certain resources, decreasing or increasing the performance depends on more layers of complexity and host system utilization. That is, the competition

for resource between guest systems may affect the performance of the individual factors of the guest machine as they rely on the host system utilization. However, it is essential to take into account such interaction when the analysis may be flawed or endeavoring to model the performance of any guest machine factors [10].

D. UTILIZATION AMBIGUITY

Utilization ambiguity is a challenge due to a number of factors which include workload, which depends on the number of the running application, users, virtualization overhead, configuration, and background processes. With utilization ambiguity, the number of application learning determines how ambiguous resources will be utilized [17]. The same applies to the number of users, background processes, and configuration.

Failing to account for the variability in the utilization will lead to inappropriate result scrutiny and performance measurement.

E. NETWORK INPUT/OUTPUT DEPENDENT

Virtualized I/O resources are shared between pools of physical and virtual servers. It includes all the aspects and components that enable data transfer at high speed including the NICs, HBAs, and CPU. With virtual resources, organizations can be able to use the network resources on demand basis and reduce the physical components [14].

IV DISCUSSION

The virtualization of computing and storage resources has provided partial reuse across a wide collection of high capacity servers by multiplexing tenants. The tenant's resource usages are based on a pay-on-use. As discussed earlier, there are various performance degradation areas are existing and they are affecting cloud computing virtualization performances [18]. Performance must be tuned for different types of application workloads. To address the virtualization performance issues, use standardized tools, servers, and architecture in a single root or multi-root virtualization devices. Although some of the important metrics like bandwidth, latency, CPU utilization, memory access, VM exits are used to estimate the performance degradation in virtualized environments.

V CONCLUSION

Through the survey presented in this paper, an attempt has been made to highlight the performance degradation issue and their origins. However, the behaviour of a cloud environment would vary depending upon several other factors including software, platform or infrastructure. Our future work would involve attempting to deal with a model towards proposing a solution to few of them.

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